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OUTCOME OF USE OF PLASTIBELL DEVICE FOR CIRCUMCISION IN PAEDIATRIC PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction – Circumcision is one of the oldest surgical procedure practiced to remove shaft skin and inner foreskin to uncover the glans.

Among various techniques for the circumcision, we have described Plastibell method which has become popular and more preferable for its advantages such as minimal tissue trauma and better cosmesis.

Aim - This article aims to analyse the safety, efficacy and outcome of plastibell circumcision in paediatric patients.

Material & Methods – This study includes 30 inpatient cases who satisfied the inclusion criteria and underwent circumcision using plastibell device at sheth L.G. hospital, AMC MET Medical college, Ahmedabad. Data on operative time, intra op and post op complications, post-operative hospital stay, cosmetic outcome and parent satisfaction was obtained and analysed.

Results – Total of 30 patients were circumcised with plastibell device with average operative time of 9 ± 3 mins. Most common post-operative complication was pain which was observed in 8 patients (26.67%). Post-op bleeding was seen in 1 patient (3.33%) due to detachment of ring. 28 out of 30 parents were satisfied with the cosmetic outcome.

Conclusion – Based on our study, plastibell circumcision is effective technique for circumcision offering lesser operating time, post-operative pain, better cosmetic outcome.

Key words – PLASTIBELL, CIRCUMCISION1

INTRODUCTION

Circumcision is one of the oldest and the most common surgical procedure in children worldwide. The procedure of circumcision thought to be at least 15000 years old.

Approximately one third of males worldwide are circumcised. It is traditional practice in Jewish and Muslims. The goal of circumcision is to remove enough shaft skin and inner foreskin to uncover the glans.

Various techniques are available for circumcision like Gomco clamp, Mogen clamp, Metal shield, Accucirc, Ali's clamp, Krive clamp, Dorsal slit (open cut) method etc. Here we have described circumcision technique using a Plastibell device. The first Plastibell circumcision was done in 1956 afterthat it has gained widespread use.

Plastibell method has become quite popular and appears to be more preferable procedure because it is quick and easy technique, causes minimal tissue trauma and minimal blood loss. It also provides good cosmetic results but sometimes this procedure may have associated with complications such as hemorrhage.

This article aims to analyse the safety, efficacy and outcome of plastibell circumcision in paediatric patients.

MATERIAL & METHODS

A total of 30 in-patient cases who underwent circumcision with Plastibell device at Sheth L.G. hospital, Ahmedabad from June 2021 to May 2022 with follow up period of 28 days were included in this study.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Infants and patients of early paediatric age group who required circumcision for various reasons.
- Patients whose parents are willing for plastibell circumcision over traditional techniques.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Anomalies of penis (i.e. chordee, concealed or buried penis, micropenis, webbed penis)
- Hypospadias or Epispadias or Ambiguous genitalia
- Active external genitalia infection

All patients underwent a thorough work up which included history taking, general and systemic examination. Pre-operative investigations were done and paediatric & anaesthetic fitness was taken. After written and informed consent taken from parents, patients were shifted electively for plastibell circumcision. A single dose of preoperative intravenous antibiotics (Injectable ceftriaxone) was given to all patients.

Various parameters such as procedure time, intra-op complications, early post-op complications, hospital stay, time taken for ring to fall off and cosmetic outcome were observed and noted.

TECHNIQUE

Similar to conventional method, preputial skin was lifted with 3 artery forceps placed at 2,6 and 10 o' clock position and lubricated tip of curved mosquito artery forceps was introduced through preputial opening to break any adhesions between prepuce and glans. After circumferentially separating prepuce from glans upto coronal sulcus, prepuce was retracted upto coronal sulcus and any smegma if present was cleaned with moistened swab. Then prepuce was reduced back and appropriately sized plastibell device was introduced through preputial opening to lie and cover upper two-third of the glans. In cases where plastibell device could not be introduced through narrow preputial opening, dorsal slit was made at 12 o'clock which was wide enough to allow plastibell to be placed adequately. Prepuce was then tied with secure surgical knot at level of groove present on device using provided thread with enough tension to permit distal necrosis of skin and prevent any oozing from cut margin. Distal preputial skin was cut circumferentially and dressing was done using neomycin ointment.

Figure 1. Placing Plastibell device

Figure 2. Cosmetic Outcome

RESULTS

According to this study on 30 patients of 7 months to 7 years age group, mean operative time observed was 9.1 (± 3.2) minutes with maximum time 14 mins and minimum time 8 mins. Most common complication observed during this study was post-operative pain which was present in 8(26.67%) patients. Other minor complications seen during study were Infection over site of skin necrosis in 2(6.67%) patients and Proximal migration of ring in 2(6.67%) patients and excess removal of skin in 2(6.67%) patients. In one patient bleeding occurred due to premature detachment of ring and required urgent surgical intervention. No major complications such as glans injury or meatal stenosis occurred during our study. Out of 30 patients, 26(86.67%) patients were discharged on POD 1 whereas 4(13.33%) patients were discharged on POD 3 owing to complications such as pain and penile oedema.

In majority of patients, plastibell was found to be separated within 10 days (8.62 ± 2.44) of follow up with earliest observed time being POD 5 and longest POD 15. 28(6.67%) out of 30 patients were satisfied with cosmetic outcome of surgery in follow up after 28 days after surgery.

	NO OF PT	PERCENTAGE
Post op pain	8	26.67
Bleeding	1	3.33
Infection	2	6.66
Glans injury	0	0
Proximal migration of ring	2	6.66
Excess removal of skin	2	6.66
Inadequate removal of skin	0	0

Table 1.
PlastibellComplications of
Circumcision

Graph 1. Timing of separation of ring

DISCUSSION

Since the introduction of plastibell circumcision, it had undergone numerous modifications, but it requires a long learning curve and lack of documentation regarding fearful complications makes it a difficult task for surgeon.

This study will pave the way for understanding plastibell circumcision, its efficacy, safety and complications faced during intraoperative, early and late post-operative period.

The following factors were taken into account:

- 1) Operative time
- 2) Post-operative complications
- 3) Post-operative stay
- 4) Time taken for bell to fall off
- 5) Parent satisfaction over cosmetic outcome

In Plastibell Circumcision, duration of operative procedure is significantly reduced as compared to conventional circumcision.

Commonly encountered complications in plastibell include post-operative bleeding and delayed separation of ring. Plastibell of inappropriate size or loose ligature can cause distal displacement of ring leading to retraction of inner prepuce and subsequent hemorrhage due to release of compression over preputial vessels.

The Plastibell ring usually falls off within 7–10 days. The ring separates faster in neonates compared to all other age categories which can be attributed to thinner preputial skin. In older children, plastibell ring takes more time to separate and can take upto 12-15 days. Delayed separation of ring can also occur due to inadequate ligature. No neonate or infant had delayed separation in this study. 8 patients having post-operative pain and surgical site infection were managed using analgesics and antibiotics. Hospital stay in plastibell circumcision is about one day, whereas 3 patients who developed pain and penile oedema were discharged on day 3. Cosmetic outcome was found to be better in plastibell circumcision.

CONCLUSION

Lesser operating time, post-operative pain, better cosmetic outcome has certainly been seen in Plastibell circumcision. Also, duration of post-operative hospital stays and time taken to return to routine daily activities was significantly less in Plastibell circumcision, making it a favourable procedure in patients in need of circumcision for different reasons of infants and early paediatric age group.

In our study in patients who underwent Plastibell circumcision, we encountered only minor complications and all those complications were managed conservatively.

REFERENCES

1. Dunsmuir, WDz, and E. M. Gordon. "The history of circumcision." *BJU international* 83.s 1 (1999): 1-12.
2. Hamza, Babatunde K., et al. "Comparison of the efficacy and safety of circumcision by freehand technique and Plastibell device in children." *African Journal of Urology* 26.1 (2020): 1-7.
3. World Health Organization. *Male circumcision: global trends and determinants of prevalence, safety and acceptability*. No. UNAIDS/07.29 E/JC1320E. World Health Organization, 2008.
4. Jimoh, Bioku Muftau, et al. "Plastibell circumcision of 2,276 male infants: a multi-centre study." *Pan African Medical Journal* 23.1 (2016).
5. Skirbekk, Vegard. "New Times, Old Beliefs: Religion and Contemporary Fertility." *Decline and Prosper!* Palgrave Macmillan, Cham, 2022. 285-300.
6. Weiss, Helen A., et al. "Complications of circumcision in male neonates, infants and children: a systematic review." *BMC urology* 10.1 (2010): 1-13.
7. Starzyk, Erin J., et al. "Infant male circumcision: healthcare provider knowledge and associated factors." *PLoS One* 10.1 (2015): e0115891.
8. Samad, Abdul, Tariq Wahab Khanzada, and Basant Kumar. "Plastibell circumcision: a minor surgical procedure of major importance." *Journal of Pediatric Urology* 6.1 (2010): 28-31.

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